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USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS.

Annotation: *By this article you can get information about advantages of using interactive methods in teaching foreign languages in primary.*

Key words: *education abroad, creativity, intellectual and communicative abilities, multimedia lecture, interactive communication, interactive whiteboard.*

The interactive method appeared in 1990. The interactive learning makes the process of learning productive that can be called a special form of organization of cognitive activities. It concerns very specific and predictable objectives. One of these is to create a comfortable learning environment in which learners feel their success, their intellectual consistency of training. The effectiveness of interactive learning techniques in teaching is increased by the requirement and demand for the successful classroom teaching.

The use of interactive learning technologies currently provides huge information capabilities, which includes organizational forms and methods of providing for the use in the educational process of modern computer and information technologies. The information technology itself means the totality of methods and means of collecting, organizing, storing, processing, transmission and presentation of information, enhance knowledge of the people and developing their ability to manage the technical and social processes. Interactive technology is unique in that it gives the opportunity to create a real language environment, where the language acts in its direct function: as a means of forming and formulating thoughts. It is genuine teaching environment, where there is space for immersion not only in the problem, but in the foreign language activity, in another culture. The study of any academic topics (environmental, political, historical, literary, etc.) is carried out on the basis of the students' study, discussion and problem solving in a foreign language with a wide employment of various opportunities and resources of the Internet.

The interactive teaching methods contain a lot of effective activities and approaches which are directed to fast the teaching process and get success.

In this regard, there can be distinguished the following methods and techniques, forms of organization in the course of employment with the use of interactive technology:

- work with the concepts – the method of self-learning, in which learners working individually, in pairs, in a group, interact with the information, where the teacher's involvement is minimal;
- a multimedia lecture; search for information on the Internet or multimedia directories; work with an interactive whiteboard;
- interactive communication (active interaction between all participants in the educational process), which becomes an important source of knowledge and experience in the implementation of active and interactive learning methods (role playing, brainstorming, group discussion, analysis of the situation);
- the use of interactive whiteboard: it's a touch screen connected to a computer when the picture on the board is passed through the projector (here increases the efficiency of the learning process, interactive space is formed; the interaction with a foreign language is exercised).

At the same time, the use of the interactive technology promotes different kinds of sensory perception of information: auditory form (the information is a complex of sounds); visual form (internal and external information is a set of visual images); kinesthetic form (the information comes in the form of a complex of sensations).

Present days interactive teaching methods require using all possible modern technologies, teaching equipment and techniques while having a lesson. Therefore modern teacher should use all the aids those are displayed in the chart above.

Aids that teacher can prepare in advance ,like charts ,flashcards and transparencies for overhead projector, will help teacher to make sure that the lesson procedures match her aims.

- Realia is very useful and easy aid,the objects that can be easily bring into the classroom and can be used to teach vocabulary, grammatical structures, for building dialogues and narratives, for games and quizzes. They include cards, menus, timetables, leaflets.

- "Using Multimedia"

Multimedia— is the combination of various digital media types such as text, images, audio and video, into an integrated multi-sensory interactive

application or presentation to convey information to an audience. Traditional educational approaches have resulted in a mismatch between what is taught to the pupils and what the industry needs.

- I recommend to focus on using multimedia technology as an innovative teaching and learning strategy in a problem-based learning environment by giving the pupils a multimedia project to train them in this skill set.

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